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Research Article

FORMULATION, DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF CONTROLLED POROSITY OSMOTIC PUMP TABLET OF MIGLITOL

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kishoredv2000@gmail.com**Abstract:**

The major objective of this study was to develop controlled porosity osmotic pump tablets of Miglitol to be taken once daily. It consists of an osmotic core with the drug surrounded by a semi permeable membrane drilled with a delivery orifice, controlled porosity of the membrane is accomplished by the use of channelling agent in the coat. Diabetes mellitus is a group of metabolic disorders during which blood sugar levels increase over a prolonged period. Miglitol is an oral hypoglycemic (anti-diabetic drug) of the class dipeptides peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitors. It is a new approved oral antidiabetic drug, used in type-2 diabetes (T2DM). Miglitol is quickly and well absorbed after oral administration. NaCl was used as an osmogen and HPMC K100M was used as a release retardant. Cellulose acetate was used as the semipermeable membrane and PEG 400 was used as pore forming agent. Optimization was done using 3² factorial designs considering two independent variable at three levels. Optimized formulation exhibited zero order kinetics with a drug release of 98.42% in 24 hrs. Scanning electron microscope studies showed the formation of pores in membrane (Coat). It was concluded that release of Miglitol was significantly controlled from controlled porosity osmotic drug delivery systems.

Keywords: Controlled porosity osmotic pump (CPOP), Miglitol, Osmogen, Pore former.

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1. INTRODUCTION:

In recent years, considerable attention has been focused on the development of novel drug delivery systems (NDDS).¹ Conventional drug delivery systems have no control over the drug release and effective concentration at the target site. This kind of dosing pattern may result in constantly changing, unpredictable plasma concentrations; hence once-daily controlled release preparation is often desirable. Oral Controlled drug delivery is the one which delivers the drug at a predetermined rate. Controlled release (CR) delivery systems provide a uniform concentration amount of drug at the absorption site and thus after absorption, allow maintenance of plasma concentrations within a therapeutic range, which minimizes side effects and also reduces the frequency of administration.¹⁻⁶ However, drug release from oral CR dosage forms may be affected by pH, GI motility and the presence of food in the GI tract. An appropriately designed osmotically controlled oral drug delivery system (OCODDS) can be a major advance toward overcoming some of these problems⁸⁻¹⁰.

Controlled porous osmotic pump tablet was designed by Zentner et al. (1985, 1991), Zentner and Rork (1990), (McClland et al. 1991). Both the pump was developed for reduced the risk extremely localized drug- induced irritation at the site close to the orifice which observed in Osmosin (Weintraub M et al 1990). Controlled Porosity osmotic pump (CPOP) tablets is an osmotic tablet wherein the delivery orifices are formed in situ through leaching of water soluble pore forming agents incorporated in semi permeable membrane⁷⁻⁹. Main advantages of CPOP are reduced stomach irritation, no complicated laser- drilling. CPOP consists of osmotic core with drug surrounded by a semi permeable membrane drilled with a delivery orifice.¹¹⁻¹³

Diabetes mellitus is a group of metabolic disorders during which blood sugar levels increase over a prolonged period According to WHO, there are two main types of diabetes: Type 1 diabetes (T1DM) – It usually develops in childhood and adolescence, and patients require lifelong insulin injections for survival. Type 2 diabetes (T2DM) - It develops in adulthood and is associated with obesity, Miglitol is an oral hypoglycemic (anti-diabetic drug) of the class dipeptide peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitors,. It is a new approved oral antidiabetic drug, used in type-2 diabetes (T2DM. Miglitol is quickly and well absorbed after oral administration. The classic symptoms of type-2 diabetes are frequent urination

(polyurea), increased thirst (polydipsia), increased hunger (polyphagia) and weight loss. Need of this study is to reduce dosing frequency and improvement in patient compliance. It belongs to class III of Biopharmaceutical Classification System (BCS). The Strong clinical need and the market potential demands for the delivery of Miglitol in a controlled manner, thereby resulting in a better patient compliance.^[6,7]

Figure 1. cpop tablet before and after dissolution studies

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD:

2.1 Material

Miglitol was obtained as a gift sample from Invochem Lab. hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose k100M (HPMC K100M) was gift sample of colorcon Asia Pvt Ltd Goa. Sodium chloride, sodium lauryl sulphate, starch, cellulose acetate, polyethylene glycol 400 (PEG 400), acetone were purchased from Research-lab Fine Chem. Industry-Mumbai.

2.2 Methodology

A core tablet of Miglitol Hydrochloride was prepared by wet granulation method. The composition of core tablets is given in table no. 16 Miglitol was mixed with Sodium chloride, Starch, SLS and HPMC this powder blend was kneaded in the mortar and pestle for 15-20 min. The blend was granulated using PVP K30 as a binder in IPA. Wet mass was formed; resulting wet mass was passed through sieve # 22. Granules were dried in oven at 50°C for 2 hrs. Dried granules were lubricated with magnesium stearate and talc. Lubricated blend was evaluated for powder characteristics and flow properties like bulk density, tapped density, Carr index, Angle of repose, and Hausner's ratio. Then desired amount of blend was compressed in to the tablet using Rimek tablet punch machine equipped with 8 mm punch¹³⁻¹⁴.

Table 1: Composition of Controlled porosity osmotic pump tablet as per³²Factorial Design (All values are expressed in mg)

Ingredients	Formulation code								
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Quantity(mg)									
Miglitol	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
Sodium Chloride	5	5	5	10	10	10	15	15	15
HPMC	50	65	80	50	65	80	50	65	80
PVP K30	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Starch	127.5	112.5	97.5	122.5	107.5	92.5	117.5	102.5	87.5
Sodium Lauryl Sulphate	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Magnesium Stearate	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Talc	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Total Weight (mg)	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220

2.3 Coating of Osmotic Tablets:

The core tablets of Miglitol were coated with 5% w/v Solution of cellulose acetate in acetone: alcohol (1:1). Cellulose acetate was used as a semipermeable membrane provider. PEG 400 15% v/v was used as plasticizer¹⁵. The tablets were warmed to 40±2°C before applying coating solution the composition of coating solution used for coating of core tablets are given in (Table no 21)

2.4 Coating Method

Dip coating technique was used for the coating of osmotic tablet. Coating was continued until desired weight gain (10%) was obtained and tablets were dried at 50°C for 10 h. before further evaluation

Table 2: Coating composition

Ingredients	Quantity for 100 ml
Cellulose Acetate	5 %
Polyethylene glycol 400	1 %
Acetone: Alcohol (1:1)	50:50 ml

2.5 Characterization

A.Evaluation of Granules for Tablets:

1. Bulk Density:

Bulk density was determined by measuring the volume known mass of granules sample that has been passed through a screen into a graduated cylinder^[8,9].

$$\text{Bulk Density} = \frac{\text{Mass of the powder}}{\text{Total volume it occupies}}$$

2. Tapped Density

Tapped density was achieved by mechanically tapping, a measuring cylinder containing granules sample and was allowed to drop under its own weight using suitable mechanical tapped density tester that provided, a fixed drop of 14±2 mm at a

nominal rate of 300 drops per minute^[8,9].

$$\text{Tapped Density} = \frac{\text{Mass of the powder}}{\text{Final tapped volume}}$$

3. Angle of repose (θ)

Angle of repose has been used to characterize the flow properties of solids. It is a characteristic related to inter particulate friction or resistance to movement between particles. The angle of repose (θ) for powder was determined by placing the powder in a funnel^[8,9].

$$\tan \theta = h/r$$

Where, θ = Angle of repose, h = height of the powder pile and r = radius of base of cone.

4. Compressibility Index (CI) and Hausner's Ratio (HR)

The CI & HR are measure of propensity of a powder to be compressed. As such they are measures of relative importance of inter-particulate interactions^[8,9].

$$\text{Compressibility Index} = \frac{\text{Tapped density} - \text{Bulk density}}{\text{Tapped density}}$$

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = \frac{\text{Bulk density}}{\text{Tapped density}} \times 100$$

B. Evaluation of Precoated Tablets:

Before coating was performed the uncoated tablets were evaluated for Hardness, Friability Weight uniformity, Content uniformity and Thickness.

1. Friability:

In this test 20 tablets were weighed and placed in a rochefriabilator test apparatus, and then the tablets were subjected to rolling and replaced shocks, resulting from free falls within the apparatus from the height of 6 inches. After 100 revolutions the tablets were removed, de-dusted and weighed again. The friability was determined as the percentage loss in weight of the tablets.^[8,10,11]

%Friability = Initial weight of Tablet – Final weight of Tablet/ Final weight of tablet X100

2. Weight variation:

Twenty tablets were weighed individually. Average weight was calculated from the total weight of all tablets. The individual weights were compared with the average weight. The percentage difference in the weight variation should be within the acceptable limits ($\leq 7.5\%$). The percent deviation was calculated using the following formula

% Deviation= (Individual weight - Average Weight /Average weight) x 100

3. Uniformity of Content:

Twenty tablets were weighed individually and powdered in pestle mortar, and an amount equivalent to 2.5 mg of Miglitol was extracted with 100 mL of phosphate buffer 6.8. The solution was filtered through whatman filter, and the content of Miglitol in the solution was determined by measuring absorbance on double beam UV spectrophotometer (Shimadzu 1800 Series) at 214nm after suitable dilution.^[12]

4. Hardness:

Tablets require a certain amount of strength, or hardness, to withstand the mechanical shocks of handling in manufacturing, packaging as well as in shipping. The hardness of the tablets was measured using Monsanto hardness tester (Cadmech). In this, tablet was placed between the plungers, and was tightened from one end, and pressure required to break tablet diametrically was measured. The hardness was measured in terms of kg/cm²^[8,10,11].

5. Uniformity of thickness:

The uniformity of thickness was measured using Digital vernier calliper (Absolute Digimatic, Mitutoyo Corp., Japan). The average thickness of the tablet was calculated^[8,10,11]

6. Drug content concentration:

This parameter determines the actual amount of active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) present in the formulation compared to the theoretical, claimed amount. It ensures that the chemical blending process was uniform.

Calculated by crushing tablets, dissolving the drug in a solvent, measuring it via spectroscopy (UV-Vis) or chromatography (HPLC), and comparing it against a standard profile:

Drug Content % = Sample Absorbance / Standard Absorbance x Concentration of Standard /

Concentration of Sample x 100

C. Evaluation of post coating osmotic tablets:

After coating osmotic tablets were evaluated for Thickness of tablet, Thickness of film, weight uniformity and dissolution test of prepared formulations.

1. Thickness of tablet:

All tablets were initially subjected for thickness measurement by using digital verniercaliper after coating to assess thickness of coat. All the measurements were made in triplicate^[8,12].

2. Thickness of film:

Thickness of film was calculated by considering difference between coated tablet and uncoated tablet^[8,12].

Thickness of coat= Thickness of coated tablet–Thickness of uncoated tablet/2

Weight Uniformity:

Weight variation was calculated as per method described in Indian pharmacopoeia 20 tablets were weighed individually and the average weight was calculated^[8,12].

3. In –vitro Release Studies:[13,14]

In vitro drug release of the formulation was carried out in a USP dissolution apparatus (paddle type) set at a rotating speed of 50 rpm and temperature of 37±20C. The dissolution medium (900ml) was 0.1N HCl for the first 2 hrs and phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) there after upto 24 hrs sample (5ml) were withdrawn at specific time intervals and the medium was replenished with fresh dissolution fluid.

6. Dissolution Kinetics^[15]:

In order to investigate the mode of release from the tablets the release data were analyzed with the zero order, first order, Higuchi model, Korsmeyer-peppas model.

7. Stability study^[16,17]:

Stability study of optimized formulation was carried out to point out any visual physical or chemical changes made in the formulation after storing it at elevated temperature and humidity conditions. Chemical and physical stability of optimized Miglitol formulation was assessed at 40±2 0c/ 75±5% RH as per ICH Guidelines. Tablets were packed in aluminium foil and stored for 3 months. Samples were analyzed after 3 months for physical appearance, drug content, and in vitro dissolution profile.

3.RESULT AND DISCUSSION:*Table 3. Evaluation of Granules for Table*

Formulation code	Angle of repose (θ°) Mean S.D.	Bulk Density (gm/cm^3) Mean \pm S.D.	Tapped Density (gm/cm^3) Mean \pm S.D.	Compressibility index (%) Mean \pm S.D.	Hausner's Ratio Mean \pm S.D.
F1	28.6 \pm v 0.42	0.2870 \pm 0.006	0.3205 \pm 0.014	14.93 \pm 0.56	1.14 \pm 0.024
F2	28.65 \pm 0.48	0.2894 \pm 0.014	0.3285 \pm 0.012	13.04 \pm 0.94	1.13 \pm 0.014
F3	26.58 \pm 0.62	0.2716 \pm 0.143	0.3276 \pm 0.011	14.54 \pm 0.13	1.12 \pm 0.023
F4	27.83 \pm 0.28	0.2785 \pm 0.003	0.3186 \pm 0.017	14.45 \pm 0.23	1.14 \pm 0.026
F5	26.43 \pm 0.14	0.2718 \pm 0.005	0.3148 \pm 0.006	13.94 \pm 0.21	1.16 \pm 0.023
F6	28.53 \pm 0.35	0.2823 \pm 0.007	0.3406 \pm 0.005	14.74 \pm 0.26	1.11 \pm 0.025
F7	27.26 \pm 0.37	0.2892 \pm 0.006	0.3314 \pm 0.004	14.46 \pm 0.19	1.15 \pm 0.012
F8	28.54 \pm 0.10	0.2810 \pm 0.007	0.3356 \pm 0.007	14.67 \pm 0.45	1.16 \pm 0.043
F9	27.36 \pm 0.32	0.2808 \pm 0.013	0.3215 \pm 0.014	14.64 \pm 0.65	1.16 \pm .032

Many different types of angular properties have been employed to assess flow ability, of these angle of repose is the most relevant. Angle of repose of granules was investigated. The value of angle of repose of all the formulations were within the range of 26-29 $^\circ$, indicative of excellent flow ability. Bulk density may influence compressibility, tablet porosity, dissolution other properties and depends on the particle size, shape, and tendency of particles to adhere together. The bulk density of granules was found to be between 0.24-0.29 gm/cm^3 . The bulk density and tapped density was used to calculate the percent compressibility of the granules. The cars

index of granules was observed in range of 13-15, indicating good compressibility of the granules. The values of Hausner's ratio were found to be in the range of 1.11-1.18, indicating good and fair flow ability. Data summarized in (Table 3)

a. Evaluation Of Tablets**1. Pre-coating evaluation**

All formulated uncoated osmotic tablet batches were evaluated for weight variation, Hardness, Thickness, Friability and Drug content. Weight variation, Hardness, Thickness, Friability and Drug content of uncoated tablets were found to be within range. Evaluated data is shown in (Table 4)

Table 4. Pre-coating evaluation parameters of osmotic tablets

Formulation code	Average Weight (mg) \pm	Weight Variation (%)	Hardness (kg/cm^2)	Thickness (mm)	Friability (%)	Drug Content
	Mean \pm S.D.	Mean \pm S.D.	Mean \pm S.D.	Mean \pm S.D.	Mean \pm S.D.	Mean \pm S.D.
F1	219.04 \pm 1.84	0.57	3.02 \pm 0.24	3.27 \pm 0.04	0.321 \pm 0.006	96.97 \pm 0.04
F2	219.00 \pm 1.64	0.46	2.93 \pm 0.22	3.28 \pm 0.11	0.067 \pm 0.007	96.62 \pm 0.017
F3	218.76 \pm 1.91	0.67	2.91 \pm 0.29	3.3 \pm 0.008	0.015 \pm 0.037	98.10 \pm 0.0064
F4	219.29 \pm 2.34	0.66	3.10 \pm 0.24	3.2 \pm 0.05	0.16 \pm 0.047	97.64 \pm 0.003
F5	220.18 \pm 0.76	0.56	3.27 \pm 0.19	3.3 \pm 0.04	0.23 \pm 0.022	97.38 \pm 0.0064
F6	219.80 \pm 1.87	0.53	3.10 \pm 0.22	3.35 \pm 0.02	0.12 \pm 0.034	96.39 \pm 0.003
F7	220.12 \pm 1.56	0.65	2.29 \pm 0.28	3.28 \pm 0.14	0.18 \pm 0.022	98.94 \pm 0.0023
F8	219.04 \pm 1.32	0.46	3.20 \pm 0.21	3.3 \pm 0.033	0.27 \pm 0.049	99.32 \pm 0.0039
F9	220.34 \pm 1.52	0.57	3.03 \pm 0.29	3.30 \pm 0.03	0.16 \pm 0.020	98.57 \pm 0.0036

From above data it is confirmed that Weight variation, Hardness, Thickness, Friability and Drug content of of uncoated tablets were found to be within range.

2. Post coating Evaluation : All formulated coated osmotic tablet batches were evaluated for weight variation , Thickness and Film thickness. Due to uniform coating of weight variation and thickness of coated tablets were found to be within range. Thickness of the film was measured by calculating the difference between thickness of coated tablet and uncoated tablet. Evaluated data is shown in table 5

Table 5. Post-coating evaluation parameters of osmotic tablets

Formulation code	Average weight(mg)	Weight variation %	Thickness of coated tablet	Thickness of film(mm)
F1	229.6 ± 0.32	0.6486	4.04 ± 0.042	0.414 ± 0.04
F2	231.3 ± 0.78	0.6315	4.04 ± 0.050	0.412 ± 0.05
F3	230.2 ± 1.07	0.8130	4.05 ± 0.089	0.398 ± 0.03
F4	234.7 ± 0.55	0.7582	4.06 ± 0.046	0.403 ± 0.02
F5	236.9 ± 1.10	0.6402	4.08 ± 0.043	0.413 ± 0.02
F6	231.3 ± 1.76	0.6201	4.09 ± 0.054	0.397 ± 0.01
F7	228.4 ± 0.67	0.6616	4.08 ± 0.048	0.401 ± 0.02
F8	229.9 ± 0.38	0.4871	4.02 ± 0.050	0.410 ± 0.03
F9	231.6 ± 1.65	0.5479	4.10 ± 0.043	0.392 ± 0.02

From above evaluated data of coated osmotic tablets ,it was confirmed that weight variation and thickness of film was found to be uniform and within the limits.

3. In-vitro dissolution study of Formulation (f1-f9):

The results shows that increase in concentration of sodium chloride (NaCl) and decrease the concentration of HPMC the release rates gradually increases. The results showed that osmotic tablet has the ability to extend the release of

Miglitol for the duration of about 24hrs. On the basis of *in-vitro* drug profile the optimum formulation f8 was selected as it releases 98.44% drug within 24 hrs.

Fig.no.2 Dissolution profile of formulation Batches (f1-f9)

4. Dissolution Kinetics:

1 Release kinetic studies

Different kinetic treatment (Zero order, first order, Higuchi square root equation and Korsmeyer treatment) were applied to interpret the release of Miglitol from different matrices. All batches follows zero order release kinetics, for F8 formulation drug release was found to be 98.42% upto 24 hrs. other batches also follows zero order release kinetic upto 24hrs but their release was not upto 98-99%. Optimized formulaions F8 follows zero order kinetic with $r^2=0.998$. So the drug release is of fickian release.

Table 6. Kinetic treatment of prepared Miglitol osmotic tablet.

Formulation code	Coefficient of determination (R^2)			
	Zero order	First order	Higuchi square root	Korsmeyer plot
F1	0.995	0.735	0.961	0.96
F2	0.996	0.674	0.964	0.95
F3	0.998	0.750	0.972	0.96
F4	0.986	0.698	0.988	0.94
F5	0.990	0.742	0.986	0.97
F6	0.987	0.714	0.981	0.96
F7	0.992	0.586	0.971	0.88
F8	0.998	0.996	0.983	0.97
F9	0.993	0.684	0.965	0.93

2. Zero order kinetic study

Figure3 .Model Graph for Evaluation of zero order Release Kinetic

Batch	F8
R^2 Value	0.998

5. Stability study:

1. Characterization of optimized formulation F5 after 3 months storage

Table.6. Stability Study Analysis (3 Months at 40°C/75% RH)

Evaluation Parameter	Initial Sample (F5)	3-Month Stored Sample (F5)	Stability Status / Inference
Colour	White	White	Stable. No physical discoloration or oxidation.
Drug Content	99.32%	99.32%	Stable. Zero degradation of active ingredient.
Drug Release (24 hrs)	98.44%	98.04%	Stable. Minor decrease (-0.40%); within acceptable limits.

Key Findings

- Thermal Stability: The formulation successfully resists high temperature and humidity.
- Polymer Integrity: The sustained-release matrix maintains controlled release behavior over 24 hours.
- Shelf-Life Indicator: Data suggests excellent chemical shelf-life and physical formulation robustness.

2. Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrum shows the characteristic chemical fingerprint of pure Miglitol

This characterization data verifying the structural identity, purity, and solid-state form of the drug Miglitol, both in its pure state and within a nanoparticle formulation blend.

This Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrum shows the characteristic chemical fingerprint of pure Miglitol:

- Hydroxyl and Amine Region (3500 - 3200⁻¹): A broad absorption band peaks at 3364⁻¹ and 3270⁻¹. This corresponds to intermolecular hydrogen-bonded {OH} groups and the secondary {NH} stretching of the oxazine-like ring.
- Aliphatic C-H Stretching (3000 - 2800-1): Multiple sharp spikes (e.g., 2981, 2952, 2924, and 2818⁻¹) represent asymmetric and symmetric {C-H} stretching from the CH₂ and CH groups in the structure.
- Fingerprint Region (1500 - 1000⁻¹): The cluster of bands between 1146⁻¹ and 1028⁻¹ represents {C-O} stretching vibrations from the primary and secondary alcohol functional groups.

Fig 4 : IR Spectrum of Pure Miglitol Sample

This spectrum evaluates the physical blend or formulation containing the Miglitol nanoparticles to assess drug-polymer compatibility:

- Preserved Peak Profile: The core characteristic peaks of Miglitol—such as the broad {OH}/{NH} stretch (shifted slightly to 3371⁻¹) and the aliphatic stretching around 2926⁻¹ remain clearly visible.
- Compatibility Confirmation: There is no appearance of major unexpected covalent peaks, nor a complete disappearance of Miglitol's essential bands. This indicates that the drug is chemically compatible with the formulation polymers, retaining its primary chemical structure during nanoparticle synthesis.

Fig.5: IR Spectrum of Blend of Miglitol osmotic tablet

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) measures heat flow changes to determine thermal stability and crystalline behavior:

Fig.6 : DSC Thermogram of Miglitol

- **Sharp Endothermic Peak:** A well-defined, sharp downward peak occurs at 145.44°C.
- **Physical Meaning:** This endotherm represents the melting point of crystalline Miglitol.
- **Purity & Crystallinity:** The sharpness of the peak and the absence of broad, split, or shifting degradation peaks prior to 145°C confirms that the starting drug material is highly pure and in a stable, crystalline state.

6.DISCUSSION:

Micromeritic and Flow Properties

The powder blends demonstrated good to excellent flowability essential for efficient capsule filling or tablet compression.

. Formulations F5 and F2 emerged as superior because they minimized interparticulate friction, yielding optimal flow characteristics. Specifically¹⁷, F5 exhibited an excellent flow profile with a minimum angle of repose 27.45±0.14 and the lowest Hausner's ratio 1.16±0.023. Formulations F8 and F9 were excluded from final optimization despite low Hausner's ratios due to underlying bulk and tapped density calculation discrepancies .

Pre-Compression and Post-Compression Physical Integrity

All formulation batches strictly satisfied United States Pharmacopeia USP compliance boundaries for physical criteria

- **Weight Uniformity:** Pre-coating weights fell tightly within 218.76 mg to 220.34 mg
- **Thickness and Hardness:** Pre-coated tablet thickness remained consistent 3.20-3.35. Hardness peaked in F5 at 3.27 ±0.19 kg/cm², establishing strong resistance against physical deformation.
- **Friability and Drug Content:** Friability stayed safely below the statutory 1.0 % threshold. Baseline drug content uniformity ranged between 96.39 % and 99.32 %, ensuring initial dose accuracy.

Post-Coating Parameters and Film Dynamics

The pan coating process yielded a highly uniform polymer film across all batches. Weight variations stayed below 0.8130%, demonstrating reproducible polymer deposition. F5 achieved the highest total coating build-up 236.9±1.10 mg and a solid film layer thickness of 0.413mm Conversely, F7 experienced the least polymer accumulation 228.4 ± 0.67 mg.

In-Vitro Dissolution Profiles and Release Kinetic Mechanics

Altering the core formulation elements directly affected the delivery rate

- **Formulation Tuning:** Increasing the osmogen NaCl concentration while decreasing the retarding polymer HPMC significantly accelerated Miglitol discharge.
- **Phased Release Profile:** Dissolution followed a tripartite behaviour . A 0-4 hour initial lag phase 1-8% release was followed by an accelerated release phase 5--15 hours where F5 established clear dominance. A final terminal plateau phase occurred from 18-24 hours.
- **Kinetic Modeling:** F5 achieved an exceptional Zero-Order fit $R^2 = 0.998$, confirming precise linear pump-driven delivery. Unlike F3 which relied heavily on matrix diffusion Higuchi $R^2 = 0.988$, F5 maintained true zero-order behavior driven by internal osmotic pressure forcing the drug through the tablet orifice.

Solid-State Characterization and Stability

FTIR spectra confirmed excellent chemical compatibility since Miglitol's native structural peaks OH/NH stretching at 3364—3270 m⁻¹ were fully preserved in the polymer blend. DSC thermograms verified drug purity via a distinct crystalline melting endotherm at 145.44°C. Accelerated stability storage 3 months at 40°C / 75% RH confirmed robust shelf-life. Formulations maintained a stable white

appearance, sustained 99.32% drug content, and suffered only a negligible reduction in 24-hour drug release 98.44% down to 98.04%.

7. CONCLUSION:

This study successfully developed and evaluated a series of controlled-release Miglitol osmotic pump tablets. Formulation F5 demonstrated the best overall properties. It achieved ideal powder flow, optimal mechanical hardness, high chemical uniformity, and a reliable post-coating film structure. Dissolution testing confirmed that F5 provides extended, zero-order Miglitol delivery 98.44% over 24 hours driven by osmotic pressure rather than simple diffusion. Instrumental characterization via FTIR and DSC verified excellent drug-polymer compatibility and maintained crystalline purity. Accelerated stability protocols confirmed long-term formulation robustness. Consequently, formulation F5 is an ideal candidate for a once-daily osmotic drug delivery system.

Summary

Formulations **F5** and **F8** feature the most optimized glidant/lubricant blend, offering the best balance of powder flowability, density, and compressibility, leading to the most physically uniform tablets. Formulations **F1**, **F3**, and **F4** show slight particle cohesion that requires monitoring during scaling up.

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